

A CONTENT ANALYSIS OF SOUTH AFRICAN UNIVERSITIES' STRATEGIC PLANS REGARDING AGENDA 2063'S TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP STRATEGIC GOAL

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Abstract

The African Union (AU) aims to enhance the integration of African nations to facilitate their development. The AU succeeded the Organization of African Unity (OAU), which was established in 1963 during the period of Africa's independence. Agenda 2063 is the current strategic framework of the AU, encompassing the period 2013 to 2063, with the year 2063 signifying the centenary of the OAU's establishment. Agenda 2063 comprises seven high-level aspirations. This paper focused specifically on the third aspiration, which advocates for a well-governed and democratic African continent that upholds the rule of law and human rights. This includes the promotion of "transformational leadership across all sectors (political, economic, religious, cultural, academic, youth, and women) on continental, regional, national, and local levels". Transformational leaders are game changers who disrupt prevailing unjust and inequitable conditions to propose a better new world for all. Thus, this study aimed to evaluate the degree to which the strategic objective of achieving universal transformational leadership in Africa, as stipulated in Agenda 2063, has been operationalized in the strategic plans proposed by leaders of African universities during the initial ten years of Agenda 2063. This objective is aligned with concerns expressed in the extant literature regarding the high failure rate of strategic plans (ranging from 50% to 90%), which raises doubts about the likelihood of the successful implementation of Agenda 2063. Additionally, this objective reflects a current research gap in the themes explored within the existing literature on African strategic plans, as such literature appears to overlook Agenda 2063 as a significant research theme. The research population for this study comprised the strategic plans of African universities. However, the research sample was limited to the strategic plans of twenty-five (25) South African universities, even though twenty-six (26) public universities are in the country. The strategic plans were obtained from the official websites of the respective universities, except for one that was not available online and was hence excluded from the study. Each strategic plan underwent content analysis to identify relevant features on Agenda 2063, where applicable. The study reveals that only two (2) South African universities' strategic plans fully integrate Agenda 2063 into their strategic goals, objectives, and Key Performance Indicators. It is worth emphasizing that the theme of transformational leadership is notably absent from the strategic plans under review, as mentioned in only two instances. These findings point to the need to urgently direct more efforts towards the effective adoption of Agenda 2063 by African universities, potentially through research and workshops.

Keywords: African Agenda 2063, African Union, Transformational leadership, South African Public Universities.

INTRODUCTION

The African Union (AU) positions itself as the new continental organization for Africa, focusing on increased cooperation and integration amongst African nations to promote the

continent's growth and economic development. Established in 2002 as the successor to the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), the AU introduced its strategic framework, Agenda 2063, in 2013. This plan aims to culminate on the centenary of the OAU, which was founded in 1963 following the independence of most African countries. The AU articulates a clear vision: "An Integrated, Prosperous and Peaceful Africa, driven by its citizens and representing a dynamic force in the global arena". This vision is operationalized through seventeen specific objectives, with a representative sample detailed below (African Union, 2015).

- *Accelerate the political and socio-economic integration of the continent;*
- *Promote peace, security and stability on the continent;*
- *Promote democratic principles and institutions, popular participation, and good governance;*
- *Establish the necessary conditions that enable the continent to play its rightful role in the global economy and international negotiations;*
- *Promote sustainable development at the economic, social and cultural levels, as well as the integration of African economies;*
- *Promote cooperation in all fields of human activity to raise the living standards of African people;*
- *Advance the development of the continent by promoting research in all fields, in particular in science and technology;*
- *Develop and promote common policies on trade, defense and foreign relations to ensure the defense of the Continent and the strengthening of its negotiating positions; and*
- *Invite and encourage the full participation of the African Diaspora as an important part of our Continent, in the building of the African Union.*

According to the African Union (AU), Agenda 2063 represents its comprehensive framework for realizing the outlined vision and objectives. Thus, it is evident that Agenda 2063 functions as the AU's strategic plan for the fifty-year period from 2013 to 2063. Strategic plans are essential components of strategic management and serve as vital tools that guide organizations in their daily operations towards achieving both short and long-term goals and objectives. These plans are developed based on an internal evaluation of the organization, along with an analysis of the external environment, thereby enabling the organization to position itself competitively within that context.

Problem Statement and Research Scope

Literature certainly recognizes the benefits of strategic plans (SPs), including the intellectual effort required to optimize the organization's resources, accountability, task scheduling and coordination, lessons learned from SWOT analyses, and fostering creativity. However, the same literature unfortunately highlights the very high failure rates of SPs, ranging from 50% to 90%, likely due to inherent flaws or poor implementation (Weston, 2020). These reported

high failure rates of strategic plan implementation cast doubt on the overall success of strategic plans, particularly regarding the strategic goal of Agenda 2063 which aims to achieve “transformational leadership in all fields (political, economic, religious, cultural, academic, youth, and women) and at continental, regional, national, and local levels” in Africa by 2063 (African Union, 2015). It is worth noting that Agenda 2063 was released with an accompanying ten-year operational implementation plan covering the period 2013 to 2023, and this paper is being written in 2024. Therefore, it is pertinent for this paper to investigate the extent to which the aforementioned strategic goal of Agenda 2063 and its operational plan have been implemented thus far. More specifically, the scope of this study is limited to Agenda 2063’s strategic goal of achieving transformational leadership in the academic field.

Theoretical Framework

Originally developed by Burns (1978) and later expanded by Bass (1985), transformational leadership has its roots in contemporary leadership theories that emphasize the importance of adapting to the complex, dynamic, and rapidly changing demands of modern society and business environments. This approach challenges traditional, behavioral, and contingency leadership models, which often view leadership as a hierarchical, top-down process that distinctly separates leaders from followers (Dickson, 2023). Such traditional leadership approaches may no longer be sufficient in today’s evolving organizational landscape (Rizvi, 2023). In contrast, transformational leaders promote change by articulating a compelling vision, inspiring others, and aligning organizational efforts toward achieving the vision. Thus, transformational leadership style often appears to be more effective, as people tend to be more inclined to follow leaders who inspire and motivate them (Northouse, 2019).

Transformational Leadership and Strategic Planning

It appears that the strategic goal identified in Agenda 2063 has selected transformational leadership from amongst the various existing leadership styles (such as transformational leadership, servant leadership, authentic leadership, situational leadership, charismatic leadership, and distributed leadership). Readers may refer to Deemie (2024) for an overview of the available leadership styles.

Transformational leadership is derived from Freire’s leadership theory, which asserts that transformational leaders must continually challenge prevailing unjust and inequitable conditions in pursuit of a better life for all (Hewitt et al., 2014). According to Santora and Bozer (2017), planning serves as a strategic tool that directs leaders based on the current situation. It is also utilized to evaluate the progress made towards their vision while addressing related challenges. Therefore, this study aims to examine the extent to which the strategic goal of achieving transformational leadership, as outlined in Agenda 2063, has been realized in the strategic plans proposed by the academic leaders of African universities. The following section is an overview of the extant literature on the strategic plans of African universities, followed by the presentation of the methodology of this study, before the presentation of its findings and recommendations for practice and future research.

Empirical Review

This literature review is based on a search of papers on Google Scholar conducted in July 2024, using the keywords "Strategic Plans" and "African Universities". The purpose of this search was to identify the major research themes that have been examined in existing studies on the Strategic Plans of African universities, and to determine the relevance of Agenda 2063 and transformational leadership within these research themes. The literature search yielded seventeen (17) relevant papers.

All seventeen reviewed papers were published between 2015 and 2024, corresponding to the first ten implementation years of Agenda 2063. Nearly half of these papers were published in 2021 and 2023, with four papers from each of those years. Eleven of the reviewed papers focus on universities from a single country, specifically from the following nations: Ghana, Kenya, South Africa and Uganda, with South Africa having the largest share of published papers. One reviewed paper examined East African universities, another focused on universities from the Southern African Development Community (SADC), and a third analyzed universities from three African sub-regions. The remaining four reviewed papers explored the Strategic Plans of universities across the entire African continent.

Three research themes appear to be tied for first place amongst the reviewed studies, with each being the focus of three papers: the collaboration-partnerships theme, the internationalization theme, and the institutional reform theme. The papers associated with the collaboration-partnerships theme concentrate on examining the Strategic Plans of African universities to identify their strategies for collaboration and partnerships with various organizations, institutions and the surrounding community.

For instance, Bekele and Ofoyuru (2021) investigated the university-society engagement strategies employed by thirty universities across fourteen African countries, while Kombo and Mwangi (2020) analyzed the collaboration and partnership strategies of both public and private universities in Kenya. Additionally, Gomwe (2019) evaluated the university-industry collaboration strategies of sixteen universities in the Southern African Universities of SADC. The reviewed papers on the internationalization theme focus on examining the strategic plans of African universities to uncover their internationalization features and strategies.

Meanwhile, the reviewed papers on the institutional reforms theme concentrate on analyzing these strategic plans to reveal the institutional reform strategies of African universities, either to become World Class Universities, adapt to globalization, or align with a new socio-political era. For example, Bisaso and Nakamanya (2020) investigated the internationalization features of the strategic plans of three public and three private Ugandan universities, while Gyamera (2015) examined the internationalization strategies of three public universities in Ghana, and Simpson (2021) explored the internationalization features of a South African university's mission and vision. Regarding the theme of institutional reforms, Sanga (2019) assessed the institutional reforms of the three oldest public universities in East Africa during the era of globalization, while Soudien (2023) studied the institutional reform strategies of the 26 South African public universities to reveal their planned strategies in the new socio-political

environment of the post-Apartheid regime. Additionally, Intsiful and Maassen (2017) analyzed the Strategic Plan of a Ghanaian institution to identify its reform strategies aimed at achieving the status of a world-class university. The research theme with the second highest representation amongst the reviewed studies is the Sustainable Development Goals theme, which includes two reviewed papers that focus on examining the Strategic Plans of African universities to uncover their strategies for achieving Sustainable Development and related Goals. For instance, Saudelli and Niemczyk (2022) assessed the Strategic Plans of three South African universities in order to determine their planned strategies for contributing to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while Ransom (2023) examined the Strategic Plan of one South African university to uncover its strategies for contributing to the development of its local community. The remaining research themes identified in the reviewed papers, namely Performance Management, Corporate Brand Personality, Academic Leadership and Leadership Styles, Entrepreneurship, Research Capacity Strengthening and Discourse Patterns, are each represented in a single paper. The paper on Performance Management explored the Strategic Plan of a South African university to assess the extent of its implementation by a Performance Management System (Mofolo and Novukela, 2024).

Moreover, the study on Corporate Brand Personality analyzed the strategic plans of seven South African Universities of Technology to determine how they reflect the corporate brand personality of their universities (Wannenburg and Roux, 2023). Meanwhile, the paper on Academic Leadership and Leadership Styles aimed to investigate the leadership styles promoted in the Strategic Plans of five high-profile South African universities (Hyde-Clarke, 2023). The reviewed paper on entrepreneurship investigated the strategic plans of eight universities from three African sub-regions to analyze the entrepreneurship models they were developing (Doh et al., 2022). Conversely, the study on research capacity strengthening assessed the strategic plans of 25 African universities and research institutes to determine the extent to which they incorporated research capacity-strengthening initiatives (Pulford et al., 2020). The reviewed paper on discourse patterns examined the strategic plans of two South African universities to analyze the shortcomings and strengths of their “marginalizing and empowering messages” (Hove, 2018).

The key research gap identified through this literature review is that Agenda 2063 does not appear as a primary research theme in any of the reviewed papers. While the term "Agenda 2063" was mentioned in three of these studies (Kombo and Mwangi, 2018; Bekele and Ofoyuru, 2021; Malefetsane and Mofolo, 2024), the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were referenced in seven papers (Kombo, Minae and Mwangi, 2018; Gomwe, 2019; Bisaso and Nakamanya, 2020; Bekele and Ofoyuru, 2021; Saudelli, 2022; Ransom, 2023; Malefetsane & Mofolo, 2024), and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were mentioned in only one paper (Ransom, 2023). In light of this research gap, the current study aims to address this issue by examining the extent to which Agenda 2063's strategic goal of achieving transformational leadership has been integrated into the strategic plans proposed by academic leaders of African universities. It is worth noting that the literature overview outlined above identified one paper on the theme of leadership styles. This paper examined the Strategic Plans of a sample of five South African universities, making it relevant to the current study since

transformational leadership is one of several leadership styles. According to Hyde-Clarke (2023), the term "transformational leadership" appears only once in one of the Strategic Plans of the universities studied. Consequently, it is essential to examine how this has been incorporated into Agenda 2063 thus far.

METHODS

Research Design and Methodology

This study employed a non-experimental, descriptive research design, using content analysis as the primary methodological approach. It examined publicly available strategic planning documents from South African public universities to describe and compare their characteristics, priorities, and alignment with the African Agenda 2063 and other development frameworks such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The strategic plans of these universities were systematically collected in July 2024 from university websites. Most documents were available as downloadable files, with others accessed directly online.

Data Collection and Sample

The population consisted of current strategic plans from public universities across Africa; however, the study applied a census approach, targeting all 26 South African public universities. Strategic plans were successfully obtained for 25 institutions. One plan could not be located and was excluded from the analysis. The final sample included 25 strategic plans, categorized by institutional type:

- Traditional Universities (12): Focused on academic and research activities.
- Universities of Technology (8): Focused on vocational training and practical skills development.
- Comprehensive Universities (5): Combining traditional academic and technological mandates (southafricaeducation, 2024).

Data Analysis

Qualitative content analysis was conducted on the manifest content using a structured coding framework. This facilitated the systematic extraction and categorization of data aligned with the study's objectives. Key variables included:

- 1) Plan Period: Start and end years covered.
- 2) Alignment with Development Agendas:
 - Agenda 2063: Goals, strategies, or indicators linked to the African Agenda framework.
 - Other Frameworks: References to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and/or Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

- 3) Mention of Transformational Leadership: Identification of themes, statements, values, or leadership approaches that reflect concepts of transformational leadership.
- 4) Institutional Descriptors: Focused on university type and academic ranking.

Ethical Considerations

This study analyzed publicly accessible documents intended for broad dissemination; therefore, specific ethical approval related to human subjects was not required. The study adhered to principles of systematic document analysis to ensure accurate and unbiased representation of the content.

Table 1: South African Public Universities and Types

No	University Name	Type
1	University of Cape Town	Traditional
2	University of the Free State	Traditional
3	University of Fort Hare	Traditional
4	University of KwaZulu-Natal	Traditional
5	University of Limpopo	Traditional
6	North-West University	Traditional
7	University of Pretoria	Traditional
8	Rhodes University	Traditional
9	Sefako Makgatho Health Sciences University	Traditional
10	University of Stellenbosch	Traditional
11	University of the Western Cape	Traditional
12	University of the Witwatersrand	Traditional
13	Cape Peninsula University of Technology	University of Technology
14	Central University of Technology	University of Technology
15	Durban University of Technology	University of Technology
16	Tshwane University of Technology	University of Technology
17	Mangosuthu University of Technology	University of Technology
18	University of Mpumalanga	University of Technology
19	Sol Plaatje University	University of Technology
20	Vaal University of Technology	University of Technology
21	University of Johannesburg	Comprehensive
22	Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University	Comprehensive
23	University of Venda	Comprehensive
24	Walter Sisulu University	Comprehensive
25	University of South Africa (UNISA)	Comprehensive
26	University of Zululand	Comprehensive

Source: <https://www.southafricaeducation.info/universities>

6. FINDINGS

This section will provide a concise overview of the Strategic Plans of the twenty-five South African public universities examined, pertaining to the aforementioned variables. It will highlight those universities that incorporated the transformational leadership strategic goal as outlined in Agenda 2063, or those that simply indicated a transformational leadership strategic

goal more generally. The section will conclude by addressing whether there is a correlation between a university's ranking, type, or the time frame of its Strategic Plan, and the presence or absence of an Agenda 2063 transformational leadership strategic goal.

6.1. Overview of the Universities' Strategic Plans

The following sub-sections present the Strategic Plans of the listed twenty-five (25) South African public universities, categorized accordingly.

6.1.1. Traditional Universities

I. University of Cape Town (UCT)

The University of Cape Town (UCT), a long-established institution founded in 1829, is currently guided by its Strategic Plan for the period 2021 to 2030. UCT is recognized as the leading university in South Africa.

However, the current Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063 or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Nevertheless, the plan includes several significant statements regarding UCT's intended contributions to the African agenda, as highlighted in the following extracts (UCT, 2021):

- “UCT’s choice to spell ‘Afrika’ with a ‘k’ is an invitation to reclaim Afrika’s agency and use it to validate the global character of the local in the 21st century. It is in this context that UCT chooses to be a global university in Afrika”.
- “UCT will take the lead in the development of the next generation of researchers, scholars and beneficial leaders for the country and for the rest of the Afrikan continent”
- “We will focus on research that highlights these unique opportunities and solve problems that matter, on the understanding that Afrika’s problems are the problems of the world”.
- “UCT students will be provided with opportunities to develop a sense of Afrikan citizenship and global citizenship”
- “We will actively focus on critical areas of impact in Afrika – for example, climate change, biodiversity, urbanisation, migration, diseases of the poor, natural resource governance, and efficiency. We will extend our Afrika-focused knowledge to a broader global reach”.
- “We will also bring an Afrikan perspective to concepts brought in from the global stage, eg artificial intelligence and autonomous transport, and extend these for Afrika’s impact and benefit while ensuring local relevance and thought leadership”.

Regarding the theme of leadership style, it is noteworthy that the Vice-Chancellor's introductory comment in UCT's Strategic Plan emphasizes that the plan is "the result of inclusive and transformational leadership at UCT", yet there is no further elaboration on this statement within the plan itself.

II. University of Free State (UFS)

Established in 1904, the University of Free State (UFS) is a traditional institution that has developed a Strategic Plan for the period spanning 2023 to 2028. Currently, UFS is ranked 9th amongst South African universities.

While the term "Agenda 2063" is not referenced in the Strategic Plan, it does emphasize UFS's commitment to making significant contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals by 2028. Although the plan does not specifically mention transformational leadership, it does highlight the university's dedication to "ethical and empowering leadership" (UFS, 2023).

III. University of Fort Hare (UFH)

The University of Fort Hare (UFH) was founded in 1966. Its Strategic Plan spans 2022 to 2026. Currently, UFH is ranked 14th amongst South African universities. Notably, the Strategic Goals outlined in this plan do not reference Agenda 2063, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), or broader considerations related to the African continent. Additionally, there appears to be no mention of leadership style as a theme within UFH's strategic objectives (UFH, 2022).

IV. University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN)

Founded in 2004, the University of KwaZulu-Natal's (UKZN) current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2023 to 2032. UKZN is ranked 5th amongst South African universities. The Strategic Plan recognizes that it has been developed within a national operating framework that includes Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

However, these contextual elements are not explicitly referenced in the strategic objectives of the plan. Nonetheless, the plan includes the following excerpt from the Vice-Chancellor's introductory remarks regarding the intended African agenda of UKZN (UKZN, 2023):

"We see the African continent, its people and its intelligentsia as an opportunity rather than as threatening competition. Furthermore, aligning our programs and scholarship to addressing national and continental issues will enable the University to attract external funding."

Regarding the theme of leadership style, it is noteworthy that it appears to be absent from the Strategic Plan of the University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN).

V. University of Limpopo (UL)

The University of Limpopo (UL), a traditional institution established in 2005, has formulated its current Strategic Plan encompassing the period 2024 to 2028. UL is ranked 15th amongst South African universities.

While the current Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063 or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it outlines a fifth Strategic Goal aimed at enhancing the university's research standing and status.

This goal includes strategic objectives that align with UL's intended contributions to the African agenda, as detailed in specific extracts from the plan (UL, 2024).

- “Conducting cutting-edge research that advances the knowledge project and contributes to the resolution of African and global challenges”.
- “Ensuring that UL’s new and existing international partnerships (particularly with other African states) are optimized”.
- “Establish an African Institute”
- “Investing in becoming the leading postdoctoral hub on the continent”.
- “Developing a multifaceted approach to deal with climate change and inequality that goes beyond teaching and research and includes integration into national and international policy networks, social activism, and the internal management of the transition within the University”.

UL’s Strategic Plan emphasizes the necessity for the university to undergo a radical transformation towards an institutional culture that “*advances the knowledge project while contributing to the resolution of African and global challenges*”. Regarding the theme of leadership style, it is noteworthy that it does not appear to be addressed in UL’s Strategic Plan.

VI. North-West University (NWU)

North-West University (NWU) was established in 2004. Its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2015 to 2025. The university ranks 12th amongst South African universities. It is noteworthy that the current Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063 or explicitly address the African continent, although it does mention the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) once. Additionally, the term "leadership" is included in the mission statement of NWU's Strategic Plan, highlighting the objective of cultivating an enabling, values-driven, transparent, and engaged leadership culture within the university (NWU, 2015).

VII. University of Pretoria (UP)

The University of Pretoria (UP) is a traditional institution founded in 1908. Its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2022 to 2026. UP is ranked 14th amongst South African universities, and its Strategic Plan emphasizes alignment with Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Notably, the reference to Agenda 2063 is not further mentioned within the plan. However, the research strategy section does address the SDGs as follows:

“Central to our research strategy is the commitment to pursue [...] research that [...] addresses complex societal challenges. Such challenges include [...] all the challenges related to the United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals”.

In terms of the leadership style theme, one may note that it does not seem to appear in UP’s Strategic Plan.

VIII. Rhodes University (RU)

Rhodes University was established in 1904, with its current Strategic Plan spanning 2023 to 2028. RU holds the 10th position amongst South African universities, and its current Strategic Plan explicitly recognizes that its development was partially influenced by Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is imperative to highlight the following strategic objective of RU's Strategic Plan and its associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), specifically related to Agenda 2063 and the SDGs (RU, 2023):

“[To] establish an accessible central portal/repository to showcase the existing expertise and knowledge generated at Rhodes University in response to global development goals (National Development Plan 2030, the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and the African Union’s Agenda 2063: the Africa we Want)”.

RU's Strategic Plan includes ethical leadership as a key objective within its strategic goals.

IX. Sefako Makgatho Health Sciences University (SMU)

Sefako Makgatho Health Sciences University (SMU) is a traditional university established in 2014, and its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2024 to 2028. SMU is ranked 20th amongst South African universities. Notably, the current Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063, and the term "Sustainable Development Goals" is mentioned only once, specifically in the preface authored by the Vice-Chancellor. Nonetheless, SMU's strategic plan includes ethical leadership as a strategic objective within one of its overarching goals (SMU, 2023).

X. University of Stellenbosch (SU)

The University of Stellenbosch was founded in 1918, with its current Strategic Plan spanning 2019 to 2024. It holds the 3rd position amongst South African universities. Its Strategic Plan was formulated taking into account Agenda 2063 and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Within the leadership theme, the plan emphasizes the importance of "committed and visionary leadership" as a fundamental component (SU, 2018).

XI. University of Western Cape (UWC)

The University of the Western Cape (UWC), established in 1959, is a traditional university that has developed a Strategic Plan for the period 2021 to 2025. Currently, UWC ranks 8th amongst South African universities, and while its Strategic Plan does not specifically reference Agenda 2063, it prominently addresses the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The first strategic goal emphasizes the necessity of aligning UWC's research initiatives with local, national, and global priorities, particularly the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (UWC, 2021).

In terms of leadership style, UWC’s Strategic Plan emphasizes promoting "values-based leadership and good governance values and principles at all levels”, recognizing these qualities as essential contributors to fostering the desired organizational culture.

XII. University of Witwatersrand (WITS)

WITS is a traditional university founded in 1922, and its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2023 to 2033. WITS is ranked second amongst South African universities. However, the present Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063 or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Nevertheless, the plan articulates the institution's commitments concerning the intended African and SDGs agenda of WITS, as evidenced by extracts from three of the four strategic focus areas of the plan (WITS, 2022):

- “Leveraging our location to build partnerships that are based on shared goals, values and achieving societal impact”.
- “Partnering with other universities to strengthen the academic project on the continent and in the Global South”.
- “Investing in becoming the leading postdoctoral hub on the continent”.
- “Developing a multifaceted approach to deal with climate change and inequality that goes beyond teaching and research and includes integration into national and international policy networks, social activism, and the internal management of the transition within the University”.

In relation to the leadership style theme, one may note that it does not seem to appear in WITS’s Strategic Plan.

6.1.2. Universities of Technology

I. Cape Peninsula University of Technology (CPUT)

The Cape Peninsula University of Technology (CPUT) is an institution of higher learning that was established in 2005. Its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2021 to 2030. CPUT is ranked 11th amongst South African universities. The Strategic Plan incorporates Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as significant external considerations influencing their new vision. However, this plan does not provide further details regarding the associated strategic objectives. Furthermore, the theme of leadership style appears to be notably absent from CPUT's Strategic Plan (CPUT, 2021).

II. Central University of Technology (CUT)

The Central University of Technology (CUT) was established in 1981. Its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2021 to 2030. CUT is ranked 22nd amongst South African universities, and its Strategic Plan acknowledges that its geographical location naturally aligns with Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The Strategic Plan articulates a vision of "a leading African University of Technology, shaping the future through innovation", despite the absence of any specifically identified Strategic Goals from Agenda 2063. Furthermore, the Strategic Plan highlights that the SWOT analysis identified the alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals as an opportunity. It is also noteworthy that

although there are no explicitly defined Strategic Goals from Agenda 2063 within CUT's Strategic Plan, the document does include several assertive statements regarding CUT's commitment to the African agenda, as evidenced by the following excerpts (CUT, 2020):

- “CUT will need to engage with key continental planning initiatives, such as the African Union’s Agenda 2063”.
- “As an African UoT, it needs to promote internationalisation with a primary focus on Africa”.
- “CUT wants to be a UoT that focuses on the challenges of Africa”.

The plan additionally highlights that the necessity to "transform the curriculum to address the challenges facing Africa and the central region" was brought to attention during consultations with stakeholders. Furthermore, the concept of leadership is articulated in the mission statement of the Strategic Plan of CUT, where it is explicitly indicated that graduates of CUT are anticipated to be "ethical and visionary leaders capable of demonstrating leadership in various contexts”.

III. Durban University of Technology (DUT)

DUT was established in 2002, and its current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2020 to 2030. The institution ranks 17th amongst South African universities. The Strategic Plan mentions Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) once, indicating its alignment with the SDGs’ timeline and the broader timeframe of Agenda 2063. The plan positions itself as integral to DUT's evolution, emphasizing its commitment to developing into a university that prioritizes sustainable practices. Although the terms "leadership" and "ethical" are not explicitly mentioned, "stewardship" is favored, particularly within the strategic goal of fostering a culture of accountability and shared responsibility (DUT, 2020).

IV. Mangosuthu University of Technology (MUT)

MUT was established in 1979, and its current Strategic Plan extends from 2020 to 2025. The university is currently ranked 24th amongst South African institutions. Notably, the Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or the African continent. However, the concept of transformational leadership is clearly articulated in the Strategic Plan, emphasizing “critical thinking, analytical and reflective evaluation, and the capacity to bring about positive change” (MUT, 2020).

V. University of Mpumalanga (UMP)

UMP was founded in 2013, and its current Strategic Plan covers the period 2023 to 2030. UMP holds the 25th rank amongst South African universities, and its current Strategic Plan does not mention the term "Agenda 2063". However, one of its performance indicators for the strategic goal of contributing to a sustainable future through partnerships is to establish collaborations with ten African Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). UMP’s Strategic Plan also explicitly identifies the implementation of an Ethical and Transformational Leadership Training program as a performance indicator for its strategic goal of effective governance and management.

Furthermore, the term "SDG" does not explicitly appear in UMP's Strategic Plan, despite its vision of an "African University leading in creating opportunities for sustainable development through innovation" (UMP, 2022).

VI. Sol Plaatje University (SPU)

Established in 2014, the Strategic Plan of SPU encompasses the period 2020 to 2024. SPU is currently ranked 26th amongst South African universities. Notably, its current Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063 or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, one of the strategic goals outlined emphasizes the importance of ethical leadership (SPU, 2019).

VII. Vaal University of Technology (VUT)

Established in 1966, VUT's current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2024 to 2033. VUT is ranked 21st amongst South African universities, and its current Strategic Plan recognizes that Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are integral to the international obligations underpinning its mandate. However, there is no further reference to these two obligations within the strategic objectives of the plan (VUT, 2023). Regarding the theme of leadership style, it is noteworthy that this aspect does not appear to be addressed within VUT's Strategic Plan.

6.1.3. Comprehensive Universities

I. University of Johannesburg (UJ)

UJ is a comprehensive university founded in 1966, with its current Strategic Plan spanning the years 2021 to 2025. UJ is ranked 6th amongst South African universities. However, its current Strategic Plan does not reference Agenda 2063 or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Nevertheless, the plan includes two strategic objectives concerning UJ's intended contribution to the African agenda, as indicated in the following extracts (UJ, 2021):

- "The university also aims to increase its stature and reputation through the quality, integrity and impact of its research endeavour, particularly as it engages with issues pertinent to the pan-African context".
- "We also intend to increase the number and stature of our partnerships with universities, selected United Nations agencies, the African Union and various embassies to secure funding and facilitate the offering of joint degrees, executive short learning programmes and the establishment of a Global Policy Institute for Africa or Leadership School".

With regard to the theme of leadership style, it is noteworthy that it does not appear to be included in UJ's Strategic Plan.

II. Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU)

NMMU is a comprehensive university established in 2005, and its current Strategic Plan spans the period 2021 to 2030. NMMU is ranked 16th amongst South African universities. The Strategic Plan recognizes Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as integral to its legislative mandate, with the SWOT analysis identifying these frameworks as

opportunities. Regarding leadership, the Strategic Plan emphasizes the university's commitment to ethical governance and leadership, prioritizing service to others over self-interest (NMMU, 2021).

III. University of Venda (UNIVEN)

UNIVEN was established in 1981, and its current Strategic Plan covers the period 2021 to 2025. UNIVEN ranks 18th amongst South African universities. Its Strategic Plan makes no mention of Agenda 2063 or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Furthermore, there is no mention of the theme of leadership style in its Strategic Plan (UNIVEN, 2022).

IV. Walter Sisulu University (WSU)

Established in 2005, Walter Sisulu University's current Strategic Plan encompasses the period 2021 to 2030. The institution is positioned 23rd in the ranking of South African universities, and its current Strategic Plan recognizes that it was developed within a context of dynamic factors, including Agenda 2063 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, the theme of leadership does not appear to be addressed in Walter Sisulu University's Strategic Plan (WSU, 2020).

V. University of South Africa (UNISA)

Established in 1873, the University of South Africa (UNISA) currently operates under a Strategic Plan that spans 2021 to 2025. UNISA is ranked 7th amongst South African universities, with the second Strategic Focus Area of its current plan emphasizing the institution's ambition to be agile while fostering an innovative, collaborative, efficient and sustainable environment. Additionally, the Strategic Plan outlines six Key Performance Indicators corresponding to this focus area, each designed to contribute to the goals outlined in Agenda 2063 and support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as detailed in Table 2 (UNISA, 2021)

Table 2: UNISA's KPIs

KPI	Agenda 2063 and SDGs Achievement Related Expected Impact
2.1	[Expected impact towards a] sustainable and well governed Higher Education Sector able to deliver on SDGs, Africa Agenda 2063, NDP 2030 Goals
2.2	[Expected impact towards a] sustainable and well governed Higher Education Sector able to deliver on SDGs, Africa Agenda 2063, NDP 2030 Goals
2.3	[Expected impact towards a] Higher Education human capital able to deliver on SDGs, Africa Agenda 2063, NDP 2030 Goals
2.4	[Expected impact towards] a reputable Higher Education Sector able to deliver on SDGs, Africa Agenda 2063, NDP 2030 Goals
2.5	[Expected impact towards] a reputable Higher Education Sector able to deliver on SDGs, Africa Agenda 2063, NDP 2030 Goals
2.6	[Expected impact towards] a well-resourced Higher Education Sector able to deliver on SDGs, Africa Agenda 2063, NDP 2030 Goals

Concerning the theme of leadership style, one may note that it does not seem to appear in UNISA's Strategic Plan.

VI. University of Zululand (UNIZULU)

Established in 1960, UNIZULU's current Strategic Plan covers the period 2022 to 2027. UNIZULU holds the 19th position amongst South African universities. The current Strategic Plan recognizes its foundation within a global context, including Agenda 2063, although it does not further elaborate on this context within the strategic objectives or reference the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) throughout the document. Notably, the plan includes a strategic goal aimed at "developing the distinctiveness of UNIZULU as an African University" (UNIZULU, 2021):

- “There are three broad aspects in which the African character of UNIZULU can be leveraged. Firstly, in terms of the University being a global node for African thought. This aspect should include African philosophical perspectives as well as both traditional and contemporary African indigenous knowledge”.
- “It would therefore be advisable to set up a Centre or Institute for African Thought as a prestigious trans-disciplinary site of African-orientated research and advocacy. The University of the Institute should further establish a credible Journal of African Thought which will focus on the presentation, discussion and critique of African epistemological knowledge frameworks and approaches”.
- “[To] ensure curricula reflect African issues and perspectives, [...] the overall curriculum perspective should proceed from the understanding that the vast bulk of UNIZULU graduates will be utilizing their knowledge and professional skills in an African context”.

Additionally, it is important to note that the theme of leadership style does not appear to be included in UNIZULU's Strategic Plan.

6.2. Clustering South African Universities' Strategic Plans

This study identified that the Strategic Plans of South African universities can be categorized into five distinct clusters, as portrayed in Table 3 below, along with the definitions of the acronyms used in that table.

- i) Strategic Plans that lack features related to the African Agenda and make no reference to Agenda 2063.
- ii) Strategic Plans that incorporate some features related to the African Agenda but do not mention Agenda 2063.
- iii) Strategic Plans that include certain features pertaining to Agenda 2063 without any inclusion of details related to the African Agenda or the strategic goals associated with Agenda 2063.
- iv) Strategic Plans that exhibit some characteristics of Agenda 2063 and incorporate details related to the African Agenda, yet do not provide strategic goals associated with Agenda 2063.
- v) Strategic Plans that contain features related to Agenda 2063, details associated with the African Agenda and establish strategic goals and key performance indicators (KPIs) pertinent to Agenda 2063.

Table 3: South African Universities' Agenda 2063 Inclusion Clusters

CN	MA	AAE	AEGK	Universities
1	No	No	No	UFS, MUT, NWU, SMU, SPU, UNIVEN, UFH
2	No	Yes	No	UMP, UJ, UCT, WITS, UL
3	Yes	No	No	CPUT, DUT, NMMU, WSU, SU, UP, UWC, VUT
4	Yes	Yes	No	CUT, UKZN, UNIZULU
5	Yes	Yes	Yes	RU, UNISA

- CN: Cluster Number
- MA: Mention of Agenda 2063
- AAE: African Agenda Elements
- AEGK: Agenda 2063 Explicit Goals and KPIs

Furthermore, regarding the theme of leadership, this study identified that only two Strategic Plans make reference to Transformational Leadership, while a limited number address Ethical Leadership, and many fail to mention the theme of leadership altogether.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study revealed that only two South African universities have incorporated Agenda 2063 into their Strategic Plans, along with specific strategic goals and key performance indicators related to Agenda 2063. Furthermore, only two universities' Strategic Plans acknowledge the concept of transformational leadership. Additionally, it appears that neither the rankings, types, nor the duration of these universities' Strategic Plans can adequately account for the adoption of Agenda 2063 or transformational leadership within the framework of their Strategic Plans.

Given the African Union's reliance on all African nations to contribute to the realization of the Agenda 2063 vision, it is essential to initiate these efforts at the institutional level. Thus, this study recommends that:

- Universities establish specific key performance indicators (KPIs) that are aligned with Agenda 2063;
- Development of key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the effectiveness of transformational leadership initiatives;
- Organizing workshops and seminars for university leadership, academic staff and strategic planning teams to enhance the understanding of Agenda 2063 and its significance to higher education;
- Promoting collaborations and knowledge-sharing networks among universities, particularly those that have successfully integrated Agenda 2063, such as UNISA, into their strategic frameworks, facilitating peer learning opportunities; and
- Conducting additional research and workshops focused on the adoption of Agenda 2063, not only within universities but also amongst African organizations.

Conflict of Interest

The study does not have any conflicts of interest

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